

D7.4 Test Report for 2nd life-Testing

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the results of second-life testing conducted on the Marbel battery module, specifically evaluating its feasibility for reuse in small mobility applications. Building on prior guidelines for second-life battery use, this study focuses on testing and analyzing the Marbel module's performance in electric scooters, e-bikes, and motorcycles.

The assessment began with defining the energy demands and usage profiles of these vehicles, followed by laboratory tests to evaluate the module's suitability. Since the tested module had not undergone prior aging, a battery lifetime model was developed to estimate its State of Health (SOH) over its first and second life.

Test results indicate that the Marbel module performs well for e-bikes and scooters, where the required power does not exceed 500W. However, it is unsuitable for motorcycles, as its 2.5 kW power limit is insufficient for speeds above 50 km/h, where power demands exceed 12.5 kW. Despite this limitation, the Marbel module's high energy density suggests it could provide extended autonomy in low-speed applications. The battery lifetime model predicts up to 1,900 cycles at 80% SOH and 3,200 cycles at 60% SOH, demonstrating its long-term viability in second-life applications.

Overall, the Marbel battery module shows strong potential for reuse in urban e-bikes and scooters, supporting sustainability goals while maintaining reliable performance in second-life applications.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

EV	<i>Electric Vehicle</i>
SOC	<i>State of Charge</i>
SOH	<i>State of Health</i>

INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents the test results from the second-life evaluation conducted on the Marbel battery module. It builds upon Deliverable 2.4, which established guidelines for second-life battery applications and suggested several possibilities. Among these, small mobility applications were identified as relatively unexplored in the existing literature.

Therefore, this task focuses on evaluating and testing the feasibility of using Marbel modules in small mobility applications, specifically considering scooters, e-bikes, and motorcycles. The evaluation process commenced with an analysis of the energy demands and characteristic usage profiles for these vehicle types. Subsequently, the Marbel module's specifications were assessed against these requirements, followed by laboratory testing of a module to determine its practical suitability for reuse.

Additionally, because the tested module had not undergone prior cycling and aging, a battery life model was developed. This model utilizes cell-level test data generated by EUT and THI within Task 7.3. It enables the estimation of the battery's State of Health (SOH) at various stages throughout its anticipated first and second life.

1. SECOND LIFE APPLICATION

After their use in electric vehicles, batteries may still retain enough energy to be repurposed for less demanding applications. This is because electric vehicles often operate close to their performance limits. For instance, a user who frequently takes long trips or requires high power may eventually find that, due to battery degradation, the vehicle can no longer meet their needs.

At this point—when the battery can no longer fulfill the application’s requirements—it is considered to have reached the end of its first life (EOL). Other factors may also contribute to a battery reaching EOL, such as the vehicle itself reaching the end of its lifespan due to manufacturing defects, aging, accidents, or regulatory requirements for battery replacement.

Because of this, the condition of a battery at the end of its first life can vary. Depending on its state, multiple second-life applications may be viable. Most commonly, batteries are repurposed for stationary applications, where weight and volume are not limiting factors, allowing capacity or power losses to be offset by adding more units. However, less-explored second-life applications exist, such as small mobility vehicles, including scooters, e-bikes, and even motorcycles.

In this study, we will define the requirements for such vehicles and conduct tests on a MARBEL module to assess whether it can meet the necessary specifications.

1.1 Marbel module and application features (scooters, e-bikes, small motorbikes)

The battery designed for this project consists of prismatic cells, whose characteristics are detailed in the Table 1. These are NMC cells known for their long lifespan and high specific energy.

Characteristic	Value	Photograph	
Technology	NMC		
Format	Prismatic		
Capacity (Ah) (Standard Discharge)	58		
Nominal Voltage (V)	3.67		
Energy (Wh)	213		
Weight (kg)	0.926		
Dimensions(mm)	148.24 x 26.66 x 105.9		
Volume (L)	0.406		
Specific Energy (Wh/kg)	230		
Volumetric Energy (Wh/L)	532.5		
Operation Voltage(V)	2.75-4.35		
Temperature Range	-20°C ~ 55°C		
Standard Charge	Voltage		C-rate
	2.75V		– 1.2C
	3.710V		– 1.1C
	3.710V	– 1.0C	
	3.763V	– 1.0C	
	3.763V	– 0.85C	
	3.870V	– 0.85C	
	3.968V	– 0.7C	
	4.100V		

	4.100V – 0.33C	
	4.218V – 0.15C	
	4.218V – 0.15C	
	4.300V	
Standard Discharge	1C	
Expected life	>2000 Cycles (100DOD) EOL=80%	

Table 1: Battery Cell characteristics

A module is composed of 12 cells in a 6s2p configuration, more information is given in the Table 2. For second-life applications, the possibility of reusing these modules is being explored. Due to their shape and weight, they could be adapted for use in small mobility vehicles such as bicycles, scooters, or small motorcycles.

Characteristic	Value	Photo
n° of cells (S or P)	6s 2p (12 cells per module)	
Nominal Voltage (V)	22.02	
Voltage Range(V)	16.5V to 26.1V	
Capacity (Ah)	116 Ah	
Energy (kWh)	2.5 kWh	
Charge power (kW)	2 kW	
Standard Discharge (kW)	2.5 kW	
Weight (kg)	13 kg	
Dimensions (LxWxH) (mm)	150x135x440	
Specific Energy (Wh/kg)	193	
Volumetric Energy (Wh/L)	511	

Table 2: Battery module characteristics

The analysis considers vehicles of various sizes, ranging from small models to the largest ones that the battery's characteristics can support. The Table 3 provides a comparison of these vehicles. The bicycle and scooter were acquired by IREC for this project, while the motorcycle represents a popular model in Spain.

From the Table 3, it can be inferred that the Marbel module will have more than enough capacity for the scooter and bicycle but will be more constrained when used in a motorcycle. In this case, power limitations may impact performance. Looking at the specific and volumetric energy values, the Marbel module shows a much higher performance compared to the batteries of the analyzed vehicles

	E-Bike IREC	Scooter IREC	Motorbike
Model	Youin-Amsterdam	Xiaomi Essential	Silence S02 L3e
Battery cost	275 €	60€	2500€
Battery Capacity	360Wh	180 Wh	5.6kWh
Battery weight	6 kg	1.1 kg	41kg
Battery Dimensions	39 x 7.6 x 11 cm	23.5 * 7 * 4.1 cm	-

Specific Energy (Wh/kg)	60	163.64	136.59
Volumetric Energy (Wh/L)	109.48	265.45	-
Charge Time	4-6 h (42V 2A)	5h (42 V 1.7 A)	9h (600W)
Max power	250 W	250 W	7.5 kW
Vehicle weight	28 kg (Bike+ batt)	12.2 kg	105kg
Vehicle Range	35 km	20 km	41km

Table 3: Electric Vehicles Characteristics

2. TEST EXECUTION

2.1 Capacity Test

The capacity test is used to assess the battery's capacity. It involves a full charge and a full discharge using a charge and discharge current of 15A. This test is crucial for evaluating the battery's state of health.

2.2 Second life profile test

To validate the battery's performance in these applications, different power profiles will be tested on the battery. To do this, a demand power profile (duty profile) is first obtained for each vehicle. Depending on the vehicle, different techniques have been used, which are defined below.

2.2.1 Electric Scooter:

The scooter acquired for the project, shown in the Figure 1, is equipped with Bluetooth connectivity.

Figure 1: Scooter used during Marbel project

Thanks to the Bluetooth connectivity of the scooter, the official app can be downloaded to a mobile device, allowing real-time monitoring of the values. In addition, there are other unofficial apps that also enable connectivity. For this project, the app *m365 Tools Pro2/G30/G2/F2*, available on the Android Play Store, was used. This app, shown in the Figure 2, allows for the recording of all necessary data (such as power, voltage of each cell and total voltage, charge status, temperature, current, and a few other parameters that are not used in this project) without the need for additional equipment.

To obtain the usage profile, the scooter was used on a 30-minute trip through the city while data was recorded with the *m365* app. The Figure 3 shows the power profiles (WATT), speed, and the evolution of current, voltage, charge percentage, and battery capacity. Despite what the datasheet indicated, the battery was subjected to power peaks of 400W.

Figure 2: App “m365 Tools” used for recording scooter profile

Figure 3: Data recorded for the scooter during driving.

2.2.2 Electric Bike

Unlike the scooter, the bicycle acquired for the project (as shown in the Figure 4) did not have Bluetooth connectivity. This made the direct recording of real-time driving data more challenging. As a result, it was decided to use an external data acquisition system. This system was specifically designed for the project and consists of the following components:

- Arduino UNO R4 WIFI
- External SSD memory board
- Accelerometer (Arduino 9-axis Motion Shield)
- Voltage and current sensors
- GPS
- External battery

The data acquisition system (DAQ) uses an Arduino as its main component, which is programmed to record the duty profile of the e-bike.

Figure 4: Electric bike and DAQ used for recording duty profile

In the Figure 5, the speed profile recorded using the GPS is shown. It is important to note that the bike is limited to a maximum speed of 25 km/h.

Figure 5: Electric Bike Speed profile obtained with DAQ with real driving

2.2.3 Electric motorcycle

To simulate the operating profile of a motorcycle, the standardized World Motorcycle Test Cycle (WMTC) speed profile is used, as shown in the Figure 6.

Figure 6: WMTC profile. Speed profile for motorcycles.

The power profile in this case is obtained theoretically. It is calculated by determining the power needed to overcome resistive forces (aerodynamic drag, rolling resistance) and to achieve the required acceleration or deceleration specified by the cycle.

The parameters needed are shown in the Table 4:

Parameter	Meaning	Value	Unit
M	Total Mass (Motorcycle + Battery + Rider)	227	kg
Cd	Aerodynamic Drag Coefficient	0.8	-
A	Frontal Area	0.6	m ²
rho	Air Density	1.225	kg/m ³
Cr	Rolling Resistance Coefficient	0.01	-
g	Acceleration due to Gravity	9.81	m/s ²
η_{break}	Overall Regenerative Braking Efficiency (Wheels to Battery)	0.7	-
$\eta_{powertrain}$	Overall Powertrain Efficiency during Propulsion (Battery to Wheels)	0.9	

Table 4: Parameters use for the mechanical modeling of the motorcycle

The methodology uses a physics-based approach to calculate the forces acting on the motorcycle at each time step. From these forces and the velocity, the mechanical power at the wheels is

determined. This mechanical power is then converted to electrical power at the battery terminals, taking into account powertrain efficiencies. The following equations are used:

- Aerodynamic Drag Force:

$$F_{aero} = 0.5 \cdot \rho \cdot C_d \cdot A \cdot v(t)^2$$

- Rolling Resistance Force:

$$F_{roll} = M \cdot g \cdot C_r$$

- Acceleration Force

$$F_{accel} = M \cdot a(t)$$

- Total Force

$$F_{total}(t) = F_{aero}(t) + F_{roll}(t) + F_{accel}(t)$$

- Mechanical Power

$$P_{mech}(t) = F_{total} \cdot v(t)$$

- Power in the battery

When vehicle is accelerating $P_{mech}(t) \Rightarrow 0$

$$P_{bat}(t) = P_{mech}(t) / \eta_{powertrain}$$

When the vehicle is braking $P_{mech}(t) < 0$, the regenerative power into the battery is:

$$P_{bat}(t) = P_{mech}(t) \cdot \eta_{break}$$

2.3 Equipment and communications

The tests were performed inside a climate chamber at 25°C, with the battery connected to a Power Cycler from the brand REGATRON. The MCU is connected to the computer using the YUCAN connector provided by the partner PTS to communicate with the cycler. The Figure 7 shows the module inside the temperature chamber.

Figure 7: Module connected to the cycler inside thermal chamber

2.4 Test Results

For the **capacity test**, first, in Figure 8, the entire process of the test can be observed, which consists of a charge to 100% using a constant current initially, followed by a constant voltage, and then a full discharge.

Figure 8: Results of Capacity Test. Voltage and Current vs time

The capacity discharged during the full discharge is 116.16 Ah, and the energy discharged is 2579.3 Wh. Given that the nominal capacity is 116 Ah and the nominal energy is 2.5 kWh, two indicators for the state of health (SOH) can be calculated: one for capacity and one for energy.

$$\text{Capacity SOH} = \frac{\text{Discharge Capacity}}{\text{Nominal Capacity}} = \frac{116.16}{116} = 100.14\%$$

$$\text{Energy SOH} = \frac{\text{Energy discharge}}{\text{Nominal Energy}} = \frac{2579.3}{2500} = 103.17\%$$

These values indicate that the battery is still performing slightly above its nominal capacity and energy specifications. This is normal, as the battery has never been cycled before. Another consideration is that the test was conducted at 15 A, which is slightly higher than C/10, a current that favors measuring higher capacities.

For all the dynamic test of the second-life profiles, two figures are obtained: one shows the evolution of current and voltage, and the other compares the required power with the power that can be extracted from the battery.

For the **Electric Scooter profile test**, Figure 9 shows a very dynamic profile, with some charging events caused by the scooter's regenerative braking system.

Figure 9: Results of Electric Scooter Profile Test: Voltage and Current Over Time.

In Figure 10, the comparison of the power profiles illustrates how the two lines overlap, indicating that the battery can comfortably follow the demand profile. The maximum discharge power is 400W, while the charging power is approximately 100W.

Figure 10: Results of Electric Scooter Profile Test: Battery Power Profile vs. Reference Power Profile.

For the **electric bicycle**, Figure 11 shows that, unlike the scooter, the bicycle does not have regenerative braking, so it only experiences discharges. In Figure 12, the comparison of the power profiles, similar to the scooter, shows that the lines overlap, indicating that the battery can supply the required power at each moment. The discharge power is lower than that of the scooter, at 250W. This is because the bicycle is pedal-assisted, meaning the cyclist also contributes some power.

Figure 11: Results of Electric Bike Profile Test: Voltage and Current Over Time.

Figure 12: Results of Electric Bike Profile Test: Battery Power Profile vs. Reference Power Profile.

For the **electric motorcycle**, the profile is quite different from that of the scooter and bicycle. First, Figure 13, it can be observed that the current peaks at 80A, much higher than the 15A required by the other vehicles. Additionally, since the motorcycle is assumed to have regenerative braking, there are regeneration peaks of up to 80A. Over the 30-minute test period, a more significant voltage drop is observed, reflecting the much higher demands of this cycle and application.

In Figure 14, it can be seen that the battery cannot fully meet the motorcycle's theoretical power profile due to the battery's maximum power limitation of 2.5kW. The theoretical profile requires approximately 12kW to reach the highest speeds of 120 km/h. However, during the less demanding parts of the cycle, the battery performs adequately, suggesting that this module should be used for motorcycles that don't require such high speeds and are more suited for urban use.

Figure 13: Results of Electric Motorcycle Profile Test: Voltage and Current Over Time.

Figure 14: Results of Electric Motorcycle Profile Test: Battery Power Profile vs. Reference Power Profile.

3. EXPECTED BATTERY LIFETIME

In WP7, ageing tests at the cell level were conducted. From this data, a battery lifetime model was developed to estimate the expected lifespan of the battery. The data used for building the model mainly consists of cycling data at different temperatures and discharge rates (C-rates). Additionally, data directly extracted from the manufacturer was incorporated to build the model. The Figure 15 shows the evolution of the state of health (SOH) throughout the test.

Figure 15: Data collected during cell tests at different conditions. Evolution of State of Health vs cycles

Based on the test data, a battery lifetime model was developed. An empirical model was created using the methodology outlined in [1], adapted to the specific data. The model, presented in the equation, relates SOH to the number of cycles, considering the effects of different temperatures and discharge rates. The fitting parameters are shown in the table, with an MAE of 5%. While this isn't highly accurate, it can be attributed to the limited data and variations across different laboratories.

$$SOH = 1 + \beta \cdot (b_T \cdot T^2 + c_T \cdot T + 1) * C_{dch}^{b_{Cdch}} \cdot Cycles^\alpha \quad (1)$$

Parameter	Value
β	0.001016
b_T	1.14E-05
c_T	-0.00679
b_{Cdch}	0.82603
α	1.31184

Table 5: Parameters for the battery lifetime SOH model.

In the Figure 16, the predictions using the model under the conditions of the tests conducted at the cell level are shown. After 1,100 cycles, a difference of around 8% in SOH can be observed, indicating that working conditions significantly affect degradation.

Figure 16: Battery Lifetime Model Results for Different Cell Test Conditions: SOH vs. Cycles.

To estimate how many remaining cycles the battery may have when it reaches the end of its first life, a lifetime simulation was performed under standard conditions (0.33 C charge, 0.7 discharge, and a temperature of 23°C) which is shown in the Figure 17. The results show that the battery is expected to last around 1,900 cycles until reaching 80% SOH and 3,200 cycles until reaching 60% SOH.

Some considerations must be made. The model only accounts for the effects of cycling, while calendar ageing—an important factor—is not included. This means that if the battery is not used, it will continue to degrade and will complete fewer cycles. Another consideration is that the state of health is set at 80% and 60% as the limits for the end of life for both first and second life, but this is an assumption, as these values vary depending on the driver and usage conditions. Some users may use the battery until it reaches 60% SOH during the first life, while others may reach the end of life in the vehicle before it hits 80% SOH

Figure 17: Battery Lifetime Simulation for Standard Conditions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presents the results of the tests conducted regarding the second life of the Marbel battery modules.

The first step in evaluating the possibility of repurposing the Marbel battery for small mobility applications was to obtain the usage profiles of several vehicles. These included an electric scooter, an electric bicycle, and a motorcycle. The scooter profile was obtained directly via Bluetooth, the bicycle profile was collected using a Data Acquisition (DAQ) system, and the motorcycle profile was derived theoretically using the mechanical equations that define the movement of a motorcycle.

The initial tests on the battery module began with a capacity test, which resulted in slightly higher state-of-health (SOH) values, exceeding 100%, i.e., above nominal values. This is due to the limited project timeline, which made it impossible to test an aged module.

The dynamic profile tests showed satisfactory results for both the bicycle and the scooter, as the maximum required power did not exceed 500W. The Marbel module could be used for these applications, although it would require slightly more space due to its larger size compared to other options.

For the motorcycle, the speed profile was much more demanding, reaching speeds of up to 120 km/h. When calculating the necessary power, it was found that for speeds greater than 50 km/h, the required power exceeded 12.5 kW—much higher than the 2.5 kW that the Marbel battery can provide. These results were confirmed by the tests, where the battery was unable to follow the reference profile due to its 2.5 kW power limitation.

In conclusion, the Marbel battery appears to be ideal for vehicles requiring speeds below 50 km/h, as it could offer greater autonomy. This is supported by the fact that the Marbel module has significantly higher specific and volumetric energy values compared to the other vehicles analyzed, which suggests that even with a lower SOH, it could still deliver better performance.

Finally, a battery lifetime estimation model was developed based on the number of cycles, indicating good performance from the cells. The model predicts that the battery can achieve up to 1,900 cycles to 80% SOH and 3,200 cycles to 60% SOH.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] J. Olmos, I. Gandiaga, A. Saez-de-Ibarra, X. Larrea, T. Nieva, and I. Aizpuru, "Modelling the cycling degradation of Li-ion batteries: Chemistry influenced stress factors," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 40, p. 102765, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2021.102765.